

Seroprevalence and Serosurveillance of Brucellosis in Human and Animal in Tertiary Care Hospital at Gujarat State of IndiaBhoya Jigisha¹, Vaidehi Mehta², Rajendrasingh Kashyap³, Jayesh solanki⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, Parul Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Parul University Vadodara, Gujarat, India²Professor and Head, Department of Microbiology, Parul Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Parul University Vadodara, Gujarat, India³District Epidemic Officer, Department of Health and Family welfare, Narmada, Gujarat, India⁴State Epidemiologist Officer, Department of Health and Family welfare, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India

Received: 25-10-2024 / Revised: 01-12-2024 / Accepted: 05-12-2024**Corresponding Author: Dr. Bhoya Jigisha****Conflict of interest: Nil**

Abstract:

Introduction: Brucellosis is considered as one of the widest spread zoonosis in the world. The importance of this contagious disease is the economic impact on livestock industry. Causes severe hazard to human health, through either direct contact with infected animals or the consumption of contaminated milk and dairy products. The rural population is primarily engaged in agriculture for which cattle are used. Due to inordinate exposure to animals and products and ignorance regarding zoonotic diseases, high prevalence of brucellosis, is not much studies in India. *Brucella melitensis* is the most virulent species that causes.

Material and Method: In present study was from, December 2022 to November 2023 Total no of fever cases 2219 suspected with brucellosis 200 tested by using Elisa technique. Also study Total 17665 pregnant animal reported total sample 17665 sample tested by using Rose Bengal test and Milk ring test.

Results: The present study was conducted from, December 2022 to November 2023. Samples of both, human and animals were tested. Total no. of fever cases in human were 2219. Out of these 2219, suspected human with brucellosis were 200. It was tested by Elisa test. All 200 human samples, tested by Elisa were Negative. Out of all these talukas maximum number of Human tested were from Sagbara 120(60%) followed by Nandod 30(15%) Dediapada 20(10%) Garudeshwer 15 (7.5%), Tilkawada 15(7.5%). All 200 human samples, tested by Elisa were Negative. Animal side Data collected from all talukas of Narmada district from GAHC portal (Govt. of Gujarat) and INAPH MIS (NDDB) reports under NAIP program (Rashtriya Gokul Mission - Govt. of India. In our study, total 17665 pregnant animal samples were tested by using Rose Bengal test and Milk ring test. The study was conducted in different talukas like, Nandod, Garudeshwar, Tilakwada, Dediapada and Sagbara. Out of all these talukas maximum number of animals tested were from Nandod 4711(26.5%) followed by Garudeshwer 3143(17.7%), Tilkawada 3528(19.9%), Dediapada 3699(20.9%) and Sagbara 2854(16.15%). Out of all these tested animals with brucellosis, confirmed case were 16. Out of these 16 positive detected animals maximum rate of positivity was seen in Sagbara 8(50%), Nandod 4(25%) followed by Garudeshwer 3(18.75%), Dediapada 2(12.5%), Tilkawada 1(6.25%), also we have notices all the diagnosed animal had pregnancy with abortion.

Conclusion: The present study revealed that the seroprevalence of brucellosis was low in human and higher in animal. In my study Maximum cases reported in the Sagbara block. Minimum cases reported by in the Tilakwada block. This study emphasises, collaborative one health approach that consists of public education, development of infrastructure for disease surveillance and reporting in both veterinary and medical fields and campaigns for control in livestock. Also the study helps to create public awareness among animal owners, farm and animal health workers on transmission and health hazards of brucellosis through community training. The implementation of public policy focused on mitigating the socioeconomic effects of brucellosis in human and animal.

Keywords: Brucellosis in human and animals, Seroprevalence, Early detection of Zoonotic disease.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Brucellosis is considered as one of the most wide spread zoonosis in the world. The importance of this contagious disease is the economic impact on livestock industry. Causes severe hazard to human health, through either direct contact with infected animals or the consumption of contaminated milk and dairy products. In human it is mainly seen in the individuals who come in contact with animal directly. [1] Brucellosis also known undulant fever Mediterranean fever or Malta fever. The rural population is primarily engaged in agriculture for which cattle are used. Due to inordinate exposure to animals and products and ignorance regarding zoonotic diseases, high prevalence of brucellosis, is not much studies in India. *Brucella melitensis* is the most virulent species that causes infections in humans, where bovine and caprine brucellosis cause by brucella aborts. The Mediterranean region of Europe, Africa, Central, south, Middle East Asia, central South America. It is significant disease for humans. [2] High brucella seropositivity states are Punjab, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Gujarat, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, and Andhra Pradesh. Species seropositivity sheep-11.55%, Cattle-8.3%, Goats-5.37%, Pigs-4.3%, Buffalo-3.6%. [3]

In Gujarat Well Established Dairy sector. – Dense population of dairy animals. AMUL & Banas Dairy are largest producers of milk from Gujarat.[4] Seroprevalence study of bovine brucellosis using indirect ELISA shows 45.80%, 22.39%, 8.57% seropositivity in Karnataka, Uttar Pradesh & Uttarakhand respectively [5](Jagapur,2013).

Incident based reporting of ADSR whenever there is an outbreak / mortality. Paper based as well as online reporting on gahc.guj.nic.in (for an outbreak / mortality). Only details of technical work done (no. of OPD, IPD, Vaccinations, Health camps etc.) is reported on monthly basis on gahc.guj.nic.in. IDSP on IHIP started effectively in district from April 2021 onwards. Case definitions used in IHIP are as in IDSP. In IHIP daily real time data entered

in S, P, L form. S for Syndromic, P for Presumptive, L for Laboratory surveillance.

Material and Method

In present study was in from, December 2022 to November 2023 Total no of fever cases suspected with brucellosis 200 tested in Human. I have studied all samples with Elisa test.

Principle

The qualitative immunoenzymatically determination of IgM class antibodies against brucella based on the Elisa technique. 'Microtiter strip wells to remove all unbound sample material horseradish peroxidase HRP labelled antihuman IgM conjugate added. The conjugate bind to the captured Brucella specific antibodies. The immune complex formed by bound conjugate is visualized by adding TmB substrate which give blue colour reaction product. The intensity of product is proportional to the amount of brucella specific IgM antibodies in the specimen. Sulphuric acid is added to stop the reaction. This Products a yellow endpoint colour. Absorbance at 450 nm is read using ELISA microwell plate reader.

Data of Animal side December -22 to November-23 Data collected from all talukas of Narmada district from GAHC portal (Govt. of Gujarat) and IN-APH MIS (NDDB) reports under NAIP program (Rashtriya). Testing done following.

1. Rose Bengal Test (RBT).
2. Milk Ring Test (MRT) /Herd test.

1. Rose Bengal test

Principle: The buffered – acid antigen stained with Rose Bengal is used for the early detection of Brucella specific agglutinins. Reagents: Rose Bengal Antigen Result: No agglutination = Negative. Visible agglutination (even slight) Positive results. The Ring test method is used for the detection of brucella antibody in milk samples. This technique is very easy to perform it especially in dairy herds.

Figure 1:

2. Milk ring test

Principle: It uses the principle of agglutination between antibodies contained in milk and dyed colored bacterial antigen of brucella to form antigen-antibody complexes that are progressively carried by the fat towards the surface of the milk and formed a blue violet ring.

Reagents: Inactivated bacterial culture of *Brucella abortus* S 99 stained with hematoxylin.

1. Carefully mix the tested milk and put 1 ml in a test tube. 2. Add 50 µl of the antigen and mix carefully. 3. Place in incubator for 1 hour at 37 C, after that for (18-20 hours) at 4 C, and then read the result.

Ring of cream equal or more colored than the underlying milk = Positive result.

Ring of cream less colored than the underlying milk = Negative result.

Figure 2:

Result

The present study was conducted from, December 2022 to November 2023. Samples of both, human and animals were tested. Total no of fever cases in human were 2219. Out of these 2219, suspected human with brucellosis were 200. It was tested by Elisa test. All 200 human samples, tested by Elisa were Negative. Out of all these talukas maximum number of Human tested were from Sagbara 120(60%) followed by Nandod 30(15%) Dediapada 20(10%) Garudeshwer 15 (7.5%), Tilkawada 15(7.5%).

Table 1: Data from December 2022 to November 2023 of Animal and Human

	Animal	Human
No of cases	17665	2219
No of tested samples	17665	200
No of lab confirmed cases	17	0

Table 2: Total no of human sample tested and total no of positive sample

Reporting site	Total no of tested sample	Total no of positive sample
Sagbara	120	0
Garudeshwer	15	0
Tilakwada	15	0
Dediapada	20	0
Nandod	30	0
Total	200	0

Table 3: Total no of samples of AFI suspected with brucellosis during Dec-2022 to Nov 2023 District Narmada

Sr no	Variabes	No of samples	Total no of tested samples
1	Human housing with dairy animals	14	Negative
2	Human housing separate housing	176	Negative
3	Contact with aborted fetus	10	Negative
	Total	200	Negative

Table 4: Cases of Acute febrile illness during Dec 2022 to Nov 2023 district Narmada

Month wise cases of AFI during Dec 2022 to Nov 2023 dist Narmada data suspected of Malaria, Dengue, Typhoid														
Sr. No	Taluka Name	Dec - 2022	Jan - 2023	Feb - 2023	Mar - 2023	Apr - 2023	May - 2023	Jun - 2023	Jul - 2023	Aug - 2023	Sep - 2023	Oct - 2023	Nov- 2023	Total
1	Dediapada	32	18	18	45	56	35	31	64	63	94	78	45	579
2	Garudeshwar	25	48	41	50	35	42	20	52	50	36	24	9	432
3	Nandod	21	17	27	19	8	32	29	42	48	91	78	90	502
4	Sagbara	19	19	14	48	32	27	36	47	68	143	101	43	597
5	Tilakwada	1	0	0	12	21	19	10	12	16	9	6	3	109
Total		98	102	100	174	152	155	126	217	245	373	287	190	2219

Animal side Data collected from all talukas of Narmada district from GAHC portal (Govt. of Gujarat) and IN-APH MIS (NDDDB) reports under NAIP program (Rashtriya Gokul Mission - Govt. of India. In our study, total 17665 pregnant animal samples were tested by using Rose Bengal test and Milk ring test. The study was conducted in different talukas like, Nandod, Garudeshwar, Tilakwada, Dediapada and Sagbara. Out of all these talukas maximum number of animals tested were from Nandod 4711(26.5%) followed by Garudeshwar 3143(17.7%), Tilkawada 3528(19.9%), Dediapada 3699(20.9%) and Sagbara 2854(16.15%). Out of all these tested animals with brucellosis, confirmed case were 16. Out of these 16 positive detected animals maximum rate of positivity was seen in Sagbara 8(50%), Nandod 4(25%) followed by Garudeshwar 3(18.75%), Dediapada 2(12.5%), Tilkawada 1(6.25%), and. Also we have notices all the diagnosed animal had pregnancy with abortion.

Table 6: Animal Population (20th Livestock census, 2019)

Cattale	Buffalo	Sheep	Goat	Total
177550	76314	21	89666	343551

Table 7: Total no of pregnant animals reported with no of abortion cases with brucellosis,

Name of Taluka	No. of Pregnant animals reported	Total no of tested sample	No. of abortion cases with brucellosis	P-Value
Nandod	4711(4710.20)	4711	4(4.80)	0.13
Garudeshwar	3143(3142.80)	3143	3(3.20)	0.01
Tilakwada	3258(3255.68)	3258	1(3.32)	1.62
Dediapada	3699(3697.23)	3699	2(3.77)	0.83
Sagbara	2854(2859.09)	2854	8(2.91)	8.88

The chi square statistic is 11. 4871. The p value is 0.021602. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

Discussion

Brucellosis is major concern worldwide but remains neglected disease. [6] France et al, 2018, Human brucellosis is characterized by various symptoms especially pyrexia of unknown origin (PUO). A prevalence of 0.8% to 6.8% from different areas has been observed in persons complaining of PUO (Sen et al., 2002). Shome et al. (2017). [13]

Earlier study conducted in Gujarat by panjarathinm and jhala found 8.5% prevalence among human cases. 13 various studies from other parts of India show seroprevalence ranging from 0.8% to 9.94% in patients with PUO. In India with the prevalence of 1.6% (2004) and 1.8% (2008). [14, 15] The present study revealed that the seroprevalence of brucellosis was low in human and higher in animal. We have notices all the diagnosed animal had pregnancy with abortion the present study was

conducted from, December 2022 to November 2023. Samples of both, human and animals were tested. Total no of fever cases in human were 2219. Out of these 2219, suspected human with brucellosis were 200. It was tested by Elisa test. All 200 human samples, tested by Elisa were Negative. Out of all these talukas maximum number of Human tested were from Sagbara 120(60%) followed by Nandod 30(15%) Dediapada 20(10%) Garudeshwar 15 (7.5%), Tilkawada 15(7.5%).

In my study Maximum cases reported in the Sagbara block. Minimum cases reported by in the Tilakwada block.

Different talukas like, Nandod, Garudeshwar, Tilakwada, Dediapada and Sagbara. Out of all these talukas maximum number of animals tested were from Nandod 4711(26.5%) followed by Garudeshwar 3143(17.7%), Tilkawada 3528(19.9%), Dediapada 3699(20.9%) and Sagbara 2854(16.15%). Out of all these tested animals with

brucellosis, confirmed case were 16, Out of these 16 positive detected animals maximum rate of positivity was seen in Sagbara 8(50%), Nandod 4(25%) followed by Garudeshwer 3(18.75%), Dediapada 2(12.5%), Tilkwada 1(6.25%), A similar finding of 13.00 % seropositivity by RBPT was also reported by Trangadia et al. (2010) and Gogoi et al. (2017). However, a lower seroprevalence rate (~5%) by RBPT was reported by Swai and Schoonman (2010), Bhanu et al. (2013), and Shome et al. (2014), while a higher seroprevalence rate (30.40 %) was reported by Pathak et al. (2016) by RBPT. A study on seroprevalence of brucellosis in cattle reported a prevalence of 7.74% on RBPT. Raghunath reddy et al. 2014. In a study carried out in Buffalos in North Gujarat patel et al. 2015 reported a prevalence of 40.67%. Although the present study restricted to small geographical area our finding agreement with above reports.

The factor associated with seropositivity for brucellosis were assisted animal delivery, drinking unpasteurised milk, drink milk products made from raw milk and eating raw meat. With this significant risk factors, human more appeared to risk of infection with brucellosis. [7] We found that consuming raw meat, Human housing with dairy animals, human housing with separate house, contact with aborted fetus, consumption of raw milk. The result was negative for all testing the sample. The analogous to outcomes of studies done in Narmada district India. [10]

Conclusion

Brucellosis places significant burdens on the human healthcare system and limits the economic growth of individuals. The implementation of public policy focused on mitigating the socioeconomic effects of brucellosis in human and animal.

In my study maximum cases reported in the Sagbara block. Minimum cases reported by in the Tilkwada block. Most commonly rural area was most commonly affected. This study emphasises, collaborative one health approach that consists of public education, development of infrastructure for disease surveillance and reporting in both veterinary and medical fields and campaigns for control in livestock. Also the study helps to create public awareness among animal owners, farm and animal health workers on transmission and health hazards of brucellosis through community training. The implementation of public policy focused on mitigating the socioeconomic effects of brucellosis in human and animal.

In addition to vaccination, culling of suspect or reactor animals based in serology used developed countries. In developed countries animal test in suspect or reactor range removed from heard and

either send to slaughter or culled by regular officials definitive testing such as bacterial culture.

Recommendation

- Development of vaccines for all the affected species of animals
- Formation of viable eradication programs
- Mass screening and castration of infected bulls
- Strong policy for culling/slaughter of infected animals.
- Inter-departmental (Animal Husbandry & Health) reporting for disease.
- Recommendations to improve reporting. Reporting should include disease / clinical symptoms wise data (For this project we have collected data from NAIP program – which collects only cow, buffalo data of AI, PD & Calving etc. This project is only implemented in aspirational districts by government.) Reporting should also include the disease wise data of other species like Sheep, goat and dogs.

References

1. Seroprevalence of human brucellosis in selected sites of central Oromia 2022, 17(12). e0269929 Dec 15.
2. Brucellosis in humans and animals (Corbel, 2006 hull and Schumacher 2018).
3. Seroprevalence of brucellosis among animal handlers in west Bengal, India an occupational health study. 2024; 10(1):1-11 published online 2024 jan 2.
4. Animal disease surveillance report 2022-023. Directorate of animal husbandry.
5. (Jagapur, et al 2013)
6. France et al, 2018
7. Satish I. ghugey, Maninder setia, et al. Human brucellosis seroprevalence and associated exposure factors among the rural population in Nagpur, Maharashtra, India. Volume 10. issue 2. February 2021.
8. Franc, K.A, Krecek, R.C, Hasler. B.N et al. Brucellosis remains neglected disease in the developing world a call for interdisciplinart action. 11 january 125 (2018)
9. Comparative of brucellosis between human and veterinary medicin 2018; 8(1)1500846 jul 24.
10. Igawe PB, Okolocha E, Kia GS, Irimiya IB, Balogum MS, Naguku P. Seroprevalence of brucellosis and associated risk factors among abattoir workers in Bauchi state Nigeria, Pan Afr Med J 2020.35.33.
11. Patel et al. 2015
12. Raghunath reddy et al. 2014.
13. Shome, R., Kalleshmurthy, T., Shankaranarayana, P. B., Gir I B Attan V A R, P., Chan D Rashek A R, N., Mohandoss, N., Shome, B. R., Kumar, A., Barbuddhe, S. B And Rahman, H. (2017).

14. Mantur BG, Akki AS, Mangalgi SS, Patil SV, Gobbur RH, Peerapur BV. Childhood brucellosis – A microbiological, epidemiological and clinical study. *J Trop Pediatr.* 2004; 50:153–7. doi: 10.1093/tropej/50.3.153.
15. Mantur BG, Biradar MS, Bidri RC, Mulimani MS, Veerappa K, Kariholu P, et al. Protean clinical manifestations and diagnostic challenges of human brucellosis in adults: 16 years' experience in an endemic area. *J Med Microbiol.* 2006; 55:897–903. doi: 10.1099/jmm.0.46097-0.